

**From Evidence to Action:
Future-Focused Recommendations for
Australia's Circular Economy**

**Prepared by: Touran Naseri
Monash University-ENS5010
Date: November 2025**

Introduction

Australia's waste system is at a turning point, with household recycling participation and confidence being still inconsistent. Part C of this White Paper moves from analysis to action, translating insights from Parts A and B. It specifically addresses evidence gaps in behavioural consistency, turning them into evidence-based recommendations to strengthen the National Waste Policy (NWP). Building on earlier findings, it targets gaps through practical actions to simplify and standardise recycling nationwide. It first presents two recommendations informed by the rapid review in Part B:

1. Introduce nationally standardised bin labels with consistent colours, symbols, and contamination guides to reduce confusion and improve sorting accuracy.
2. Expand local drop-off points for e-waste, batteries, and soft plastics to improve accessibility beyond kerbside collection.

Next, a Risk Matrix was applied to assess the potential for uneven adoption of the labelling system and resulting policy fragmentation across councils. This structured decision-support tool quantifies both the severity and likelihood of inconsistent implementation affecting household recycling participation, enabling policymakers to prioritise mitigation strategies effectively (EPA Victoria, 2023).

Finally, a Scenario Planning approach explores how these recommendations might perform under future conditions, ensuring policy resilience amid technological, financial, and behavioural uncertainties (Cook et al., 2014). The following sections apply these tools to evaluate the feasibility, risk, and long-term resilience of the proposed actions.

Evidence-based Recommendations

This section advances two evidence-based policy recommendations to strengthen Australia's NWP by addressing the everyday decision points that shape household recycling behaviour. Grounded in the rapid-review findings (Part B), this section applies the Claim–Evidence–Reasoning framework and SMART criteria (Bjerke & Renger, 2017) to produce two scalable, inclusive, and adaptable recommendations designed to enhance behavioural consistency and implementation feasibility across policy and funding contexts. These recommendations also support Australia's Waste Action Plan 2024 target to halve per-capita waste generation and achieve an 80 % average resource recovery rate by 2030 (DCCEEW, 2024).

Recommendation 1: National Bin-Labeling Standardisation

Adopt a single, nationally consistent bin-labelling system with fixed colours, intuitive icons, and common-contaminant warnings across all councils to improve sorting accuracy. Led by DCCEEW and state EPAs, the framework would guide local implementation and harmonise packaging messages nationwide. This implementation would occur in stages: national specifications by 2026, local pilots from 2026 to 2027, and a broader rollout by 2027. The success would be assessed through reduced contamination (–20%), improved sorting accuracy (+10%), and $\geq 80\%$ household comprehension (see Appendix A).

This recommendation addresses the behavioural and standardisation gaps identified in Part A. The rapid review found that convenience and clarity are the strongest predictors of correct recycling, with clear, consistent labelling improving sorting accuracy by 5–12 percentage points (O'Dwyer et al., 2022; Bernardo et al., 2023). If replicated nationally, these effect sizes could translate to hundreds of thousands of tonnes of recyclables being correctly sorted each year, significantly advancing Australia's circular economy and landfill diversion targets. Standardised labels would therefore simplify decision-making at the point of disposal and reinforce social norms through on-pack and at-bin cues.

By unifying communication and reducing behavioural friction, this policy advances NWP objectives on information consistency and circularity, delivering measurable behavioural improvements and cost savings in waste processing while supporting long-term national recycling participation. It aligns with NWP Principles 3 and 5, promoting consistency and transparency (DCCEEW, 2018).

Recommendation 2: Expand and Promote Local Drop-Off Points for Problem Materials

Adopt a coordinated approach to expand and publicise council and retail drop-off points for non-kerbside materials such as e-waste, batteries, soft plastics and textiles. Led jointly by state EPAs and local councils with stewardship partners, this network would ensure metro residents travel no more than 3 km to a site and provide hub-and-spoke access in regional areas. This implementation milestones include network mapping by Q1 2026, a 25 % increase in sites by Q4 2026, and annual KPI reviews. The results will be measured by higher capture (+30 % batteries/e-waste; +15 % soft plastics/textiles) and ≥ 90 % resident awareness (see Appendix A).

Evidence from the Part B review indicates that removing logistical barriers, such as distance and unclear hours, yields sustained participation gains of 10–35% (O’Dwyer et al., 2022; Nguyen et al., 2022; Landells et al., 2022). Part A further identified the absence of localised data and transparency, both of which this network would generate through standardised reporting and open dashboards. If replicated nationally, such gains could divert thousands of tonnes of hazardous or high-value materials from landfills each year, directly advancing Australia’s circular economy targets.

Drop-off hubs complement kerbside systems, providing visible and trusted collection points that reinforce behavioural norms and enable feedback loops through community dashboards, mirroring the multi-component model found to be most effective in the rapid review. It aligns with NWP Principles 3 and 5, promoting consistency and transparency (DCCEEW, 2018).

Together, these recommendations address both behavioural and logistical barriers in Australia’s recycling system.

Risk Assessment

Australia's decentralised waste governance means that councils vary in their infrastructure, budgets, and recycling systems, increasing the likelihood that a uniform labelling scheme will be adopted unevenly, which can confuse residents and undermine behavioural outcomes. Therefore, the principal risks associated with Recommendation 1 are implementation inconsistency and stakeholder resistance. To evaluate feasibility, a Risk Matrix (EPA Victoria, 2023) consistent with the ISO 31000:2018 Risk Management Guidelines (International Organisation for Standardisation, 2018) was applied to assess the likelihood and impact of policy fragmentation and uneven adoption. Risks were rated on a 5-point scale (Rare = 1 to Almost Certain = 5; Minor = 1 to Severe = 5), following the EPA Victoria (2023) definitions. This structured approach enables policymakers to prioritise risks by severity and probability, supporting evidence-based planning within environmental governance frameworks (Pascarella et al., 2021).

Table 3 (Appendix B) summarises the assessment: uneven uptake of bin labels was rated as high-impact, high-likelihood; stakeholder resistance was rated as medium-impact, medium-likelihood; and public confusion during rollout was rated as medium-impact, medium-likelihood. These risks can be mitigated through targeted education campaigns, early consultation, shared funding incentives, and phased rollouts, reducing residual risk to low–medium. Residual ratings and a colour-coded 5×5 heat map illustrating likelihood versus impact are provided in Appendix B. This structured process also clarified inter-council governance dependencies and highlighted where early consultation can prevent implementation setbacks.

Overall, the assessment confirms that while the initiative is achievable, success depends on national consistency, intergovernmental collaboration, and transparent communication to sustain alignment, strengthen public trust, and advance the NWP's circular-economy objectives. This process operationalises NWP Principle 5 (evidence-based decision-making) and supports SDG 12.5, reinforcing transparency and adaptive learning within circular-economy governance (United Nations, n.d.). These risk insights directly inform the scenario exploration that follows, ensuring that recommendations remain robust under diverse governance and behavioural futures.

Exploring Possible Futures

Scope Setting and Tools

A foresight approach was applied to anticipate how Australia's recycling system could plausibly unfold. Stakeholder analysis and an issues tree were used to define the scope of uncertainty, revealing governance interdependencies and root-cause barriers that shape household recycling behaviours and policy coordination across councils. The insights from these scoping exercises informed the development of scenario axes and variables for futures exploration.

Scenario Framework

Scenario planning was then used to test the resilience of the two recommendations under uncertainty, rather than to predict a single outcome, recognising that Australia's waste-governance system is dynamic and influenced by technological, financial, and behavioural shifts (Cook et al., 2014; Redford et al., 2013). This method recognises that Australia's waste-governance landscape is dynamic, influenced by shifts in technology, funding capacity, and public trust.

- Predetermined elements: existing waste-collection infrastructure; legislative commitment to the NWP.
- Drivers: community environmental values; digital communication platforms.
- Uncertainties: council capacity (high ↔ low); public adoption (high ↔ low).

These form the axes of a 2×2 Scenario Matrix summarised in Appendix C.

These futures reinforce the risk assessment findings that early consultation and shared funding incentives are essential to prevent fragmented implementation. The four plausible futures are Smart Circular Nation, Fragmented Effort, Grassroots Innovation, and Policy Fatigue which illustrates contrasting trajectories. Early signals include state-funding announcements, mobile-app adoption rates, and progress toward label harmonisation, while a wild card, a rapid AI-based waste-sorting breakthrough, could transform infrastructure needs. Across all futures, the dual-intervention package remains most robust: standardised labelling drives consistency, and accessible drop-off points sustain participation under diverse governance conditions.

Insights and Implications

Recommendation 1 performs best under high-adoption futures, whereas Recommendation 2 remains resilient even when council capacity is low, demonstrating complementary strengths. Together, these scenarios illustrate that a dual-intervention pathway, standardised labelling and

accessible drop-off infrastructure offers the most adaptive, evidence-based route to achieving the NWP and SDG 12.5 objectives.

Major conclusion

This White Paper demonstrates that Australia's NWP can be strengthened through consistent evidence use and behavioural insight. Part C builds on the findings of Parts A and B, which identified gaps in data transparency, local evidence, and behavioural integration, as well as the importance of convenience, feedback, and social norms. It translates these insights into two actionable recommendations: national bin-labelling standardisation and expanded local drop-off points. It is supported by risk and scenario analyses, these strategies provide adaptive, scalable pathways for coordinated governance and evidence-based behavioural design, advancing NWP objectives and SDG 12.5 on responsible consumption and production. Collectively, these strategies provide adaptive, scalable pathways toward a circular-economy transition.

AI Declaration

In preparing this essay, I used generative AI tools, specifically ChatGPT and Grammarly, to enhance my APA 7th referencing, improve grammar, and clarify my expression. However, all critical arguments, analyses, and selections of sources are my own work. The AI tools were used solely for support in presentation and referencing, not for content generation or evidence fabrication.

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Appendix A
SMART table

Table 1: Recommendation 1, Standardise Household Bin Labels Nationally

SMART	High-Funding Scenario	Low-Funding Scenario
Specific	Implementing: DCCEEW & state EPAs; Delivery: local councils; Partners: APCO/brand owners; Impacted: households incl. MUD/CALD. Scope: all kerbside streams incl. FOGO; bilingual/visual variants. Goal: simpler, more accurate sorting via uniform cues	Implementing: state EPAs + pilot LGAs; Delivery: early-adopter councils; Partners: APCO; Impacted: pilot households. Scope: core streams first; phased CALD variants. Goal: prove national spec in pilots.
Measurable	Targets (12 months post-pilot): -20% contamination; +10 pp correct-sort; ≥80% label comprehension. KPIs: contamination %, correct-sort %, comprehension score; Monitoring: 6-monthly audits + public dashboard.	Targets (12 months): -12% contamination; +6 pp accuracy; ≥70% comprehension. KPIs/Monitoring: as left, limited to pilot LGAs.
Achievable	National templates, training, and comms toolkit; capex modest vs avoided reprocessing losses; councils have comms/audit capacity.	Reuse existing council assets (bins, stickers, web/app); smaller print runs; shared templates/support; staggered training.
Relevant	Advances NWP goals (consistency, circularity, resource recovery); addresses fragmentation from Part A; operationalises convenience lever from Part B.	Same alignment; focuses on “learn then scale” to de-risk multi-jurisdiction roll-out.
Time-bound	Spec Q2-2026 → Pilots Q3–Q4-2026 → staged state rollouts through 2027; 6-monthly KPI reporting & iteration.	Spec (lite) Q2-2026 → 3–5 LGA pilots Q3–Q4-2026 → expand 2027 subject to KPI thresholds.

Table 2: Recommendation 2, Expand & Promote Local Drop-off Points for Problem Materials

SMART	High-Funding Scenario	Low-Funding Scenario
Specific	Implementing: state EPAs & councils with stewardship schemes (batteries, e-waste, textiles, soft plastics); Hosts: libraries/retail/depots; Impacted: households, especially MUD/remote. Scope: metro density ≤ 3 km; hub-and-spoke regional model; unified signage/app map. Goal: accessible diversion beyond kerbside.	Implementing: councils + stewardship partners in priority suburbs/towns; Scope: lean network at civic sites first; shared signage kit; app map MVP. Goal: demonstrate uptake & safe diversion.
Measurable	Targets (12 months in pilot regions): +30% battery/e-waste capture; +15% soft-plastics/textiles; $\geq 90\%$ awareness of nearest site. KPIs: kg captured/site, visits/site, contamination incidents, awareness score; Reporting: quarterly.	Targets (12 months): +18% battery/e-waste; +8% soft-plastics/textiles; $\geq 75\%$ awareness. KPIs/Reporting: as left, lighter cadence.
Achievable	Leverages depots/retail partners; co-fund via stewardship + council budgets; scalable staffing; established LGA precedents.	Start with existing depots/libraries; volunteer/community partners; minimal fit-out; targeted comms bursts.
Relevant	Delivers NWP circularity & community-engagement aims; reduces kerbside contamination; improves equity and trust via visible infrastructure/data.	Same alignment; prioritises high-impact postcodes/streams for early wins.
Time-bound	Network mapping Q1-2026 \rightarrow +25% sites by Q4-2026 \rightarrow quarterly promotions; annual KPI review to guide scale/standards.	Mapping Q2-2026 \rightarrow +12% sites by Q4-2026 \rightarrow biannual review to plan staged growth.

Appendix B
Risk Assessment Table

		Consequence →				
Likelihood		Minor (1) Local or minor impact	Moderate (2) Short-term service disruption or public confusion	High (3) Nation-wide behavioural setback or credibility loss	Severe (4) Major policy failure or loss of public trust	Catastrophic (5) Systemic collapse of policy or governance
	Almost Certain (> 80 %)	Potential Risk (5)	High Risk (7)	Severe Risk (9)	Severe Risk (10)	Extreme Risk (12)
	Likely (50 – 80 %)	Low Risk (3)	Potential Risk (5)	High Risk (7)	Severe Risk (9)	Extreme Risk (10)
	↓ Possible (30 – 50 %)	Low Risk (2)	Low Risk (3)	Potential Risk (5)	High Risk (7)	Severe Risk (9)
	Unlikely (10 – 30 %)	Low Risk (2)	Low Risk (3)	Low Risk (4)	Potential Risk (5)	High Risk (7)
	Rare (< 10 %)	Low Risk (1)	Low Risk (2)	Low Risk (3)	Low Risk (4)	Potential Risk (5)

Figure 1: shows the likelihood–consequence relationship for identified risks under Recommendation 1, following ISO 31000:2018

Scale Definitions

- Likelihood: Rare (< 10 %), Unlikely (10–30 %), Possible (30–50 %), Likely (50–80 %), Almost Certain (> 80 %).
- Consequence: Minor=local/minor impact; Moderate=short-term service disruption or public confusion; High=nation-wide behavioural setback or credibility loss; Severe=major policy failure or loss of public trust.

Colour-coding Guide

- Low Risk – Acceptable; manage through routine monitoring.
- Potential/Low-Medium Risk– Requires scheduled review and minor mitigation.
- Medium/Significant Risk – Significant; active mitigation and oversight required.
- High/Severe/Extreme Risk – Unacceptable; immediate coordinated action required.

The matrix was populated by mapping potential behavioural, operational, and financial risks arising from inconsistent bin-label uptake.

Table 3: Risk assessment matrix for recommendation 1

Risk Description	Likelihood	Consequences	Raw Risk Rating	Justification	Mitigation Strategy	Residual Rating
Inconsistent adoption of bin labels across councils	High	High	● High	Differences in council waste systems and funding may result in uneven implementation, causing confusion among residents.	Develop a national coordination framework with federal funding incentives. Provide standardised design templates, technical support, and progress monitoring.	● Low–Medium
Stakeholder resistance due to cost or system incompatibility	Possible	Moderate	● Medium	Councils may perceive the change as costly or misaligned with local recycling contracts.	Conduct early stakeholder consultations; co-design templates; provide transitional grants or resource-sharing models.	● Low–Medium
Public confusion during transition phase	Possible	Moderate	● Medium	Residents may be uncertain about new colour codes or labelling meanings during initial rollout.	Implement a national communication and education campaign; phase rollouts through pilot trials; offer visual guides via council apps and websites.	● Low–Medium
Reputational risk if results are not immediate	Possible	Moderate	● Medium	Lack of early visible outcomes could reduce public trust in the initiative and policy credibility.	Set realistic short-term indicators and communicate incremental achievements publicly; release transparent performance reports.	● Low
Funding constraints or delays	Unlikely	High	● Low–Medium	Competing budget priorities at the state or council level could delay implementation.	Secure intergovernmental agreement for shared funding responsibility; integrate the initiative with existing recycling infrastructure upgrades.	● Low

Behavioural inconsistency was rated as the highest composite risk, reinforcing the importance of early coordination and communication.

Source: Adapted from EPA Victoria (2023) and ISO 31000 (2018), Clauses 6.4–6.6.

Appendix C
Scenario Planning Matrix Table

Figure 2: Two-by-Two Scenario Matrix: Council Capacity vs Public Adoption

	High Public Adoption	Low Public Adoption
High Council Capacity	<p>Smart Circular Nation, coordinated funding, strong digital communication, and community enthusiasm deliver a cohesive national system. Recycling targets are exceeded through consistent labels and efficient infrastructure.</p> <p>Policy levers: maintain incentive grants, feedback loops, and cross-jurisdictional audits to sustain engagement and verify outcomes.</p>	<p>Fragmented Effort, well-resourced councils implement policy, yet inconsistent engagement and public scepticism limit recycling gains. Participation depends on enforcement rather than motivation.</p> <p>Policy levers: invest in targeted awareness campaigns and transparent performance reporting to rebuild public trust.</p>
Low Council Capacity	<p>Grassroots Innovation, Councils lack resources, but active citizen groups and social enterprises fill the gap through creative reuse hubs, peer-to-peer repair networks, and community-led drop-off schemes.</p> <p>Policy levers: provide micro-grants, shared training kits, and state mentoring programs to scale community innovation.</p>	<p>Policy Fatigue, both institutional capacity and public interest decline. Label reforms stall, drop-off points underperform, and recycling rates stagnate amid confusion and low trust.</p> <p>Policy levers: introduce periodic public reviews and adaptive funding to prevent policy stagnation and re-energise participation.</p>

Axes:

Council capacity and public adoption were identified as the two key uncertainties most likely to determine the success of the bin-labelling and drop-off recommendations. Together, they capture the tension between governance capability and community participation that drives policy outcomes within Australia’s decentralised waste system. This axis pairing was prioritised because capacity and adoption most strongly determine whether national policy translates into consistent local outcomes.

Notes:

Early signals, federal and state funding announcements for circular-economy pilots; growth in mobile recycling-app subscriptions; media attention to label-harmonisation progress.

Wild card, a rapid AI-based waste-sorting breakthrough that automates material separation, potentially disrupting the need for behavioural interventions.

Relative resilience ranking (1 = low to 4 = high): Smart Circular Nation (4); Grassroots Innovation (3); Fragmented Effort (2); Policy Fatigue (1).

Interpretation:

Across the four plausible futures, the combined strategy, standardised labelling plus accessible drop-off infrastructure, proves most resilient. It enables flexible policy adjustment under varying governance and adoption conditions, reinforcing the evidence-based, adaptive intent of the NWP.

Source: Adapted from Cook et al. (2014) and Redford et al. (2013). Scenario planning applied to test recommendation resilience under uncertainty.